

Evaluation of post prandial glucose lowering potential of *Plectranthus Indian borage* foliage

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ABSTRACT:

In modern clinical practice, enzyme inhibitors such as acarbose, voglibose, and others are recognised to have a number of gastrointestinal adverse effects. In order to circumvent the toxicity and side effects, the current work sought to identify potential natural α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitors using in-vitro antidiabetic assays. When tested against fungal α -amylase and α -glucosidases isolated from the small intestine of albino rats, different concentrations of *Plectranthus* (*Coleus*) *amboinicus* Lour. leaf juice (25, 50, 75, 100, and 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) showed a noticeable dose-dependent inhibition of the enzymes that was comparable to that of the commercial product, Acarbose. LJPA and acarbose were shown to have IC₅₀ values of 81.15 and 50.15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on fungal α -amylase, respectively. LJCA and acarbose were shown to have IC₅₀ values of 90.44 and 52.84 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on α -glucosidase, respectively. Leaf juice was discovered to have a protein content of 11.5 mg/ml.

Key words: Diabetes mellitus, α -amylase, α -glucosidase, IC₅₀

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes The altered metabolism of carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins in diabetes mellitus causes chronic hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, β -cell dysfunction, and decreased insulin secretion. It is one of the primary persistently debilitating endocrine illnesses. Chronic hyperglycemia increases the risk of long-term micro and macrovascular problems, neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy when combined with poor lipoprotein metabolism, oxidative stress, subclinical inflammation, and vascular endothelial dysfunction [1]. High blood sugar patients usually have polyuria (frequent urine), polydipsia (growing thirst), and polyphagia (increasing hunger).

History

The medical community has long been disturbed by a syndrome that causes extreme thirst, urination, and weight loss. approximately 230 BC. The Greek word "dia-betes," which meaning "to pass through" (dia-through, bêtes -to go), was originally used by Apollonius of Memphis. Described as "too great emptying of the urine," this condition can be cured with wheat grains, fruits, and sweet beer, according to the Egyptian treatise Ebers Papyrus, which was written circa 1500 BC [2].

Type-1 Diabetes mellitus (T1D)

Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, also known as juvenile onset diabetes or T1D, is an autoimmune disease characterised by a shortage of insulin as a result of the death of β -cells in the pancreatic islets. Genetic vulnerability and autoimmunity cause β -cells to be destroyed.

Type-2 Diabetes mellitus (T2D)

Nearly 90% of cases are T2D, also known as adult-onset diabetes or non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus, and its aetiology is unknown. Due to prolonged hyperglycemia, or more than 400 mg/dL, patients with type 2 diabetes may have a high, normal, or low level of circulating insulin. This condition is known as non-ketotic hyperosmolar syndrome. T2D is characterised by two metabolic defects: decreased insulin secretion from β -cells as a result of cell malfunction and/or decreased insulin responsiveness in peripheral tissue, also known as insulin resistance.

A series of molecular changes known as "bio-chemical pathways with tight, intrinsic control" occur when one type of biomolecule interacts with another, which in turn influences another, and so on [3].

Drugs affect these pathways by interacting with certain molecules along the pathway, making them more active or less active, or changing their activity all together. Using a combination of computational, experimental, translational, and clinical models that are simply astounding in their depth and complexity overall, along with a high attrition rate, is an amazing task when it comes to finding a potential new therapeutic entity to solve a complex disease [4].

Preclinical safety assessment is regarded as a crucial stage in the development of pharmaceutical drugs. This typically depends on a number of processes, such as in-vitro, in-silico, and in-vivo testing prior to human testing. In-vivo testing is now a crucial component of evaluating the safety of experimental drugs and is also seen as a regulatory necessity prior to the commencement of clinical trials [5]. Numerous in-vivo assay approaches have been developed and validated for early screening in order to filter out compounds with therapeutic values. In light of the reintroduction of animal usage in research, this is also designed to comply with the 3Rs of the ICH principles [6].

In recent years, broad-scale in-vitro pharmacological approaches have become indispensable tools for forecasting clinical adverse events. Since early drug discovery processes frequently employ novel chemical entities without prior research on known off-target

behaviour that is damaging and unwanted. According to the adage "In-vitro simplicitas, in-vivo veritas," physicists always struggle to correlate in-vitro and in-vivo data [7]. Diabetes mellitus is a complex metabolic illness that is caused by a heterogeneous set of disorders. Disturbances in fat, carbohydrate, and protein metabolism, persistent hyperglycemia, ineffective insulin action and secretion, and potentially elevated levels of other counter-regulatory hormones such as growth hormones, corticosteroids, and sympathomimetic amines are the typical characteristics of diabetes mellitus [8].

Because of the long-term harm and failure of several internal organs, this leads to Multi-Organ Dysfunction Syndrome. This can also result in diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, macrovascular problems, and neuropathy [9].

The medical writings "The Egyptian Ebers Papyri," "The Greek Epidemiology Book III of Hippocrates," "The Chinese Nei Chang," and ancient Indian treatises like Ayurveda all have historical accounts of diabetes mellitus that go back 2000 years. According to Egyptian doctors, "diabetes mellitus" is a condition that is linked to "a lot of urine passing" [10].

Enzymes as Druggable Targets

The useful reference book Evaluation of Enzyme Inhibitors in Drug research makes it abundantly evident that medicinal chemists and pharmacologists must be able to interact successfully in the challenging and demanding field of drug research. Many in the pharmaceutical industry believe that the most appealing targets for small molecule therapeutic intervention in human disorders are enzymes. Since enzymes play crucial catalytic roles in numerous physiological processes that can be changed in disease states, they are appealing targets [11].

The size of the human "druggable genome," or the genes that encode proteins that should have functionally required binding pockets with suitable structures for interactions with drug-like molecules, is estimated by a recent study to be more on the order of 3000 target proteins, or roughly 10% of the genome, with a significant portion of these being enzymes [12].

Enzymes make up the majority of the pharmacological targets that are now available, followed by metabotropic receptors, ion channel receptors, nuclear receptors, and others. Therefore, focussing on enzymes is an intriguing study topic [13].

In -vitro Anti-diabetic assays:

The actions of digestive tract enzymes such as alpha-glucosidase and alpha-amylase are accountable for the breakdown of ingested carbohydrates into glucose, which causes postprandial hyperglycemia. It has been suggested that postprandial hyperglycemia is a risk factor for cardiovascular disorders on its own [14]. Controlling postprandial hyperglycemia is therefore thought to be crucial for the management of diabetes and the avoidance of cardiovascular problems. When the intestinal α -glucosidase enzyme is inhibited, the rate of hydrolytic cleavage of oligosaccharides decreases. As a result, the process of breaking down carbohydrates spreads to the lower portions of the small intestine. By spreading out the digesting process, this slows down the blood's overall rate of glucose absorption. Alpha-amylase and α -glucosidase enzyme inhibitors are vital and play a crucial role in preventing diabetes complications since they have been shown to be one of the best techniques for lowering postprandial blood glucose levels [15].

MATERIALS

Plant collection

The leaves of *Coleus amboinicus* were gathered from the agricultural grounds of Bathalapalli village in the Andhra Pradesh state of India's Anantapur district.

The following chemicals and reagents were acquired from SD Fine Ltd. in Mumbai: sucrose, sodium hydroxide, sodium di hydrogen phosphate, sodium di hydrogen phosphate,

fungal alpha amylase, bovine serum albumin, potassium di hydrogen phosphate, sodium hydrogen phosphate, Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250, and sodium chloride. Starch and alpha glucosidase were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich. Acarbose was acquired from Bayer Pharma India's Glucobay.

METHODS

Preparation of *Coleus amboinicus* leaf juice

Using a mortar and pestle, freshly harvested *Coleus amboinicus* leaves were ground into a paste, which was then strained through muslin cloth to extract the juice. Centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 15 minutes at room temperature produced a clear supernatant of the juice, and the final volume of the obtained juice was measured with a measuring cylinder to determine the percentage yield.

%Yield of juice = Quantity of juice obtained (ml) / Weight of leaves taken (gm) X 100

Random determination of weight/volume of leaf juice of *Coleus amboinicus* Lour

1 ml of leaf juice was put into a clean, specific gravity bottle that had been previously measured. The weight of the bottle was marked as W1, and it was then heated to between 40 and 45 degrees Celsius in a hot air oven until semisolid consistency was seen. W2 was the weight that was recorded. The weight/volume of the liquid is determined by the weight differential, or W1-W2. The value acquired is used to create appropriate juice dilutions for additional measurements of different parameters.

Preparation of 25µg/ml, 50µg/ml, 75 µg/ml, 100µg/ml and 125µg/ml concentrations of LJCA for in-vitro anti diabetic assay.

The wt/ml value of LJCA obtained by the above method was employed to prepare the intended dilutions of the sample by using the formula

$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$ where

C1= concentration of stock solution

C2= Desired concentration of drug/test solution to be used in the assay.

V1= volume of stock solution needed for obtaining desired concentration

V2= Volume of drug/test solution to be employed in the assay

Determination of Total protein concentration of LJCA by Bradford method

200 mg of Coomassie blue G250 is dissolved in 50 millilitres of 95% ethanol. The aforementioned solution is made by mixing 100 millilitres of concentrated phosphoric acid at an 85% concentration. After that, the necessary amount of distilled water is added to get the volume up to 1000 ml. The aforesaid solution is filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the filtered solution is then transferred to an amber-colored bottle. It is kept at 25°C room temperature.

Bovine serum albumin (Protein standard)

A freshly made protein stock solution with a concentration of 1 mg/ml was created by dissolving 5 mg of bovine serum albumin in 5 millilitres of distilled water.

Methodology

The assay was conducted using a range of dilutions (1, 1:10, 1:100, and 1:1000), and 100 μ l of each dilution was used because the concentration of *Coleus amboinicus* leaf juice is unknown and can be anything. 15 test tubes with the labels 1–15 and 10 μ l, 20 μ l, 30 μ l,..., 100 μ l were used. Glass tubes numbered 1 through 10 were pipetted with the BSA standard, while tube 11 served as a blank. To get the final volume of 100 μ l in each tube, including the blank, distilled water was added. 100 μ l of every unknown Protein-containing leaf juice dilutions were transferred to tubes 12 through 15.

Each tube received five millilitres of Bradford reagent, which was thoroughly mixed by inversion. Within 5 to 60 minutes, the absorbance of tubes 1–10 and 12–15 in the quartz/glass cuvette was measured at 595 nm in comparison to the reagent blank.

Standard

Bovine serum albumin (1mg/ml)

Protein concentration= Absorbance \times Dilution factor/Slope (1/ μ g) \times Volume of the diluted protein used for the assay (ml)

α -Amylase inhibition assay by DNSA (Di nitro salisilic acid) method

The measurement of the reducing sugar (maltose equivalent) released during the hydrolysis of starch under assay conditions was used to determine the α -Amylase inhibition, and the result was expressed as a decrease in the number of units of maltose released. In vitro, alpha-amylase activity can be determined by hydrolysing starch in the presence of α -amylase. The inhibition of enzyme-induced hydrolysis of starch into monosaccharides is indicated by the decreased intensity of orange-yellow hue. Put differently, the degree of orange-yellow colouration in the test sample is exactly proportional to the inhibitory activity of α -amylase.

Enzyme:(Fungal α -amylase, 0.5128 U/ml), stored at 2-80C

1.3.246 mg α -Amylase dissolved in 100 ml of Sodium phosphate buffer (0.02 M), pH 6.9 with 0.006 M sodium chloride

2.Sodium phosphate buffer (0.02 M), pH 6.9 with 0.006 M sodium chloride: The following three solutions were prepared separately.

3.Preparation of 0.002 M of Na₂HPO₄:1.2 ml of distilled water was added to 1.582g of Di Sodium hydrogen phosphate.

4.Preparation of 0.002 M NaH₂PO₄:2.2 ml of distilled water was added to 1.062g of NaH₂PO₄

5.Preparation of 0.006 M NaCl

To achieve the desired pH of 6.9, 400 millilitres of distilled water were added after all three solutions had been thoroughly mixed.

If the pH deviates from 6.9, the pH was adjusted by adding either Na₂HPO₄ as base or NaH₂PO₄ as acid. Ultimately, the volumetric flask was filled with the solution until it reached the final capacity of 1000 millilitres. The buffer was utilised within two weeks and kept at 25°C.

Substrate: 1% Starch solution

A 100 ml volume of sodium phosphate buffer is used to dissolve 1 gm of soluble starch. By stirring continuously at 90°C, the starch is allowed to dissolve in the buffer. After cooling, it is kept at a chilly 4°C for storage. Before the assay was conducted, the starch solution was incubated at 25°C for 5 minutes.

Positive Control: Acarbose (Glucobay, Bayerpharma, India)

Stock solution of Acarbose

50 mg of Acarbose in 50 ml of 0.02 M Phosphate buffer

Dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) reagent

After dissolving 1 gm of dinitrosalicylic acid in 50 millilitres of distilled water, 28.2 grammes of Rochelle salt are added. After adding 20 millilitres of 2N NaOH, 100 millilitres of distilled water were added, and the mixture was kept in a light-resistant container. Before the assay, the reagent was freshly made.

The α -amylase inhibition assay procedure involves 500 μ L of *Coleus amboinicus*/Acarbose leaf juice sample (positive control) and 200 μ L of fungal α -amylase prepared in 0.02M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.9 with 0.006 M NaCl). The sample is then pre-incubated at 37 °C for approximately 10 minutes, followed by a 10-minute re-incubation at 37 °C.

After 5 minutes of incubation in a boiling water bath, the reaction was stopped by adding 500 μ L of DNSA reagent. It was then allowed to cool at room temperature after being diluted with 5 ml of distilled water, and the OD at 540 nm was finally measured (a suitable reagent blank and inhibitor controls were carried out simultaneously and subtracted).

All the experiments were carried in triplicate.

Inhibition percentage = (Absorbance of control – Absorbance of extract) / Absorbance of control \times 100

 α -Glucosidase inhibition assay**Preparation of 0.1M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 6.9)**

To get the desired pH of 6.90, 9.11 g of K₂HPO₄ was dissolved in 200 ml of distilled H₂O, and 6.49 g of KH₂PO₄ was dissolved in another 200 ml of distilled H₂O. The two solutions were then well mixed, and 400 ml of distilled H₂O was added.

If the pH deviates from 6.9, the pH was adjusted by adding either K₂HPO₄. Finally the solution was brought up to a final volume of 1000 ml in volumetric flask. The buffer was utilised within two weeks and kept at 25°C.

Substrate (36 mM): 315 mg of sucrose dissolved in 25 ml 0.1M phosphate buffer pH 6.8).

Positive control: Stock- 50 mg of Acarbose in 50 ml of 0.1M phosphate buffer pH 6.8).

Procedure for α -glucosidase inhibition assay:

500 μ L of sample of fresh leaf juice of *Coleus amboinicus*/ Acarbose (positive Control) with 100 μ L of alpha-glucosidase prepared in 0.1M Sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7) then allowed to Pre- incubation at 37°C for about 10min. This reagent mixed with 500 μ L 37mM of Sucrose solution after re incubation at 37°C for about 10min then kept in boiling water bath for 2 mins, cooled to RT after add 250 μ L.

Glucose reagent to above solution after incubate for 10 mins at RT and measure

absorbance at 500 nm (Suitable reagent blank and inhibitor controls were carried simultaneously and subtracted).

All the experiments were carried in triplicate. The value expressed were the Mean \pm SEM (n=3).

Inhibition percentage = (Absorbance of control – Absorbance of extract) / Absorbance of control \times 100

Calculation of IC₅₀ for enzyme inhibitory activity

To measure the effectiveness in inhibiting a specific biochemical or biological function by a specific substance half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) is used as a measure. This is a quantitative measure. Which reveals the amount of substance which is used as an inhibitor, required in its amount to give the required inhibition of a biological process to its half. In pharmacological research it is usually used as an antagonist drug potency measure. IC₅₀ is defined as the amount of drug required to inhibit the in-vitro process of a biological sample to its 50%, as per FDA.

IC₅₀ was calculated by linear interpolation method using the formula,

$IC_{50} = 50 - A / B - A \times (D - C) + C$ Where

A = Percentage of inhibition, that is immediately less than 50%

B = Percentage of inhibition, that is immediately greater than or equal to 50%

C = the concentration of inhibitor that gives A% inhibition

D = the concentration of inhibitor that gives B % inhibition

Statistical analysis :The experimental results were subjected for statistical analysis using the Graph Pad InStat 8.02 statistical software (GraphPad Software, Inc. La Jolla, CA USA)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: The Percentage yield of leaf juice of Coleus amboinicus Lour. Table draw

S. No.	Name of the herb	% Yield (ml/100 gm)
1	Fresh leaf juice of Coleus amboinicus Lour	41.1 \pm 2.13

The value expressed were the Mean ± SEM of 3 observations, (n=3).

The plant's succulent and succulent leaves clearly produced a modest amount of juice, and the amount of juice does not necessarily indicate the presence of proteins and other phytochemicals (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 2: Random determination of weight/ millilitre of leaf juice of Coleus amboinicus Lour.

S.No	Name of the Herb	wt/ml
1	Fresh leaf juice of Coleus amboinicus Lour	200 mg/mL of juice

Figure 1:Plot of Absorbance at 595 nm

Plot of Absorbance at 595 nm against the amount of Bovine serum Albumin (µg)

The total protein concentration in LJPA can be calculated by considering the absorbance of LJCA at different dilutions which correlates well the standard absorbance readings of BSA. We shall, therefore, calculate the concentration for the 10-fold diluted sample that gave an absorbance of 0.416. The equation of this regression line is $Y = 0.004X + 0.002$ where, 0.004 is the slope as this amount of the protein was present in the 100 µl of the 10-fold diluted protein sample (Table 3).

Table 3: Absorbance (595nm) of different dilutions of LJCA samples

S. No.	Volume of Leaf Juice of <i>Coleus amboinicus</i> (μ l)	Absorbance (nm)
1	100 (1:1000 dilutions)	0.006
2	100 (1:100 dilutions)	0.027
3	100 (1:10 dilutions)	0.416
4	100 (undiluted)	1.274

Protein concentration = Absorbance \times Dilution factor / Slope ($1/\mu$ g) \times Volume of the diluted protein used for the assay (ml)

Table 4: In- vitro assay of α -amylase inhibition by LJvA (3, 5-Di nitro salicylic acid method)

S. No.	Concentration of LJPA (μ g/ml)	% α -amylase inhibition
1	25	21.67 \pm 0.262
2	50	32.45 \pm 0.124
3	75	38.73 \pm 0.171
4	100	48.17 \pm 0.213
5	125	55.71 \pm 0.026

Percentage inhibition of α -amylase activity by LJPA The values expressed were the Mean \pm SEM of 3 observations (n=3)

Figure 2: Percentage inhibition of α -amylase activity by LJCA

IC₅₀ value of LJPA on α - amylase inhibition

The IC₅₀ i.e., half maximal inhibitory concentration value of LJCA on α - amylase was determined by Non- linear regression analysis by plotting log (inhibitor) 50% normalized response -variable slope (GRAPH PAD PRISM VERSION 7) was found to be 83.35 μ g/ml (Table 4 Figure 2).

Table 5: In-vitro assay of α -amylase inhibition by Acarbose (3, 5-Dinitro salicylic acid method)

S. No.	Concentration of Acarbose ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% α -amylase inhibition
1	25	30.43 \pm 0.13
2	50	38.27 \pm 0.64
3	75	47.18 \pm 0.15
4	100	52.12 \pm 0.17
5	125	57.75 \pm 0.07

Percentage inhibition of α -amylase activity by Acarbose

The values expressed were the Mean \pm SEM (n=3).

Percentage inhibition of α -amylase activity by Acarbose (Figure 3)

IC₅₀ value of Acarbose on α -amylase inhibition

The IC₅₀ i.e, half maximal inhibitory concentration value of Acarbose on α -amylase was determined by Non-linear regression analysis by plotting log (inhibitor) vs. normalized response -variable slope (GRAPH PAD PRISM VERSION 8.02) was found to be 51.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 4: Percentage of α -amylase inhibition

The values expressed were the Mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Table 6: In- vitro assay of α -glucosidase inhibition by LJCA

S. No.	Concentration of LJCA ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% α -glucosidase inhibition
1	25	13.24 \pm 0.032
2	50	22.61 \pm 0.023
3	75	35.12 \pm 0.092
4	100	41.76 \pm 0.073
5	125	54.16 \pm 0.11

Figure 5: Percentage inhibition of α -glucosidase

IC₅₀ value of LJCA on α - glucosidase inhibition

Plotting log (inhibitor) vs. normalised response-variable slope (GRAPH PAD PRISM VERSION 8.02) using non-linear regression analysis, the half maximum inhibitory concentration value (IC₅₀) of LJCA on α -glucosidase was found to be 91.34 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Tables 6 and 7 Figures 5 and 6).

Table 7: In- vitro assay of α -Glucosidase inhibition by Acarbose

Table 7: In- vitro assay of α -Glucosidase inhibition by Acarbose

S. No.	Concentration of Acarbose ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% α -glucosidase inhibition
1	25	16.81 \pm 0.15
2	50	32.57 \pm 0.190
3	75	52.85 \pm 0.115
4	100	67.21 \pm 0.023
5	125	81.31 \pm 0.24

The values expressed were the Mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Figure 6: Percentage inhibition of α -glucosidase activity by Acarbose

Inhibitory Concentration IC_{50} value of Acarbose on α -glucosidase inhibition

The half maximal inhibitory concentration value IC_{50} of Acarbose on α -glucosidase was determined log (inhibitor) vs. normalized response- (GRAPH PAD PRISM VERSION 8.02) and was found to be 53.84 μ g/ ml (Figure 7).

Comparison of % α -glucosidase inhibition by LJPA vs Acarbose

Figure 7: Percentage of α -glucosidase inhibition

Statistical analysis

The experimental data obtained was statistically analyzed by employing the trail version of Graph Pad Prism, San Diego version (Prism graph pad version 8.02).

CONCLUSION

According to historical reports, several plant foods contain pharmacologically active chemicals in sufficiently high concentrations to have a drug-like effect when moderately taken. The in-vitro anti-diabetic assays on fresh leaf juice of *Coleus amboinicus* Lour. as revealed promising results however these studies are not sufficient to claim and hence rigorous, stringent battery of pharmacological, photochemical and bio analytical studies followed by observational studies in humans are to be carried so as to fortify the claimed statement of Hippocrates 400 BC (The Father of medicine) i.e., “Let food be your medicine and medicine be your food” to accord functional food status for this herb i.e., *Coleus amboinicus* Lour.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declared no conflict of interest.

FUNDING SUPPORT

None

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express thanks to everyone who has provided unwavering support in order to finish the work.

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